

APPENDIX H

Log file example

Table H.1
Example of log file

Time	Group	Test Taker	Message
13:22:30	1	Student 2	Hello, we can talk on the Chat and thus agree.
13:22:33	1	Student 3	Hello, we can talk on the Chat and thus agree.
13:23:01	0	Student 5	Let's start
13:23:04	1	Student 6	Let's start
13:23:04	0	Student 4	Hello, we can talk on the Chat and thus agree.
13:23:19	1	Student 3	What do they see on their tablets?
13:23:29	1	Student 2	I see the figure that we must find and you?
13:23:32	1	Student 6	I see atoms
13:23:41	0	Student 1	Let's start
13:23:43	1	Student 3	It seems that we all see the same
13:23:50	1	Student 2	How do you think we have to do it?
13:23:52	1	Student 6	How do you think we have to do it?
13:23:54	0	Student 4	Let the game begin.
13:24:07	0	Student 1	Let the game begin.
13:24:08	1	Student 3	There are some colors but I don't know what they are for, let's continue.
13:24:13	1	Student 2	I think everyone can only select atoms of the color that was assigned to them.
13:24:15	0	Student 5	I see atoms and you?
13:24:25	1	Student 6	Ya, let's continue?
13:24:26	1	Student 3	Ya, let's continue?
13:24:30	0	Student 4	It seems that we all see the same
13:24:41	0	Student 1	It seems that we all see the same
13:24:48	1	Student 2	I already know which atom to choose
13:24:49	1	Student 6	I think we must find in the sky the molecule of the figure And you?
13:24:52	0	Student 4	We were all assigned a color that we can select.
13:24:53	0	Student 5	It seems that we all see the same
13:25:03	1	Student 3	I think there is more than one possible molecule
13:25:10	1	Student 2	It's all clear, are we still?
13:25:10	0	Student 1	There are some colors but I don't know what they are for, let's continue.
13:25:18	1	Student 6	You have to agree on which atoms to choose
13:25:18	0	Student 4	Ya, let's continue?
13:25:27	0	Student 1	Ya, let's continue?